

Neust-College of Criminology Extension Services; Impact Assessment

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Abstract:- This is a descriptive quantitative study to determine the impact of the extension services conducted by the NEUST-College of Criminology for the past five years from 2016-2020. The study conducted in the City of Cabanatuan with 25 respondents. Results revealed that extension services conducted by the college has possible impact on economic and social aspects while there were no impact on the environment, on the overall the extension services of the college has likely impact. It is then concluded that the NEUST-College of Criminology Extension Services has marked its impact to the community evident in the high overall impact. Hence, it is recommended that the college extension services continue and be strengthened by delivering initiatives that will have a greater impact on the community's lives.

Keywords:- *Impact Assessment, Criminology, Extension Services.*

I. INTRODUCTION

Evaluation is defined as the process of gathering and analysing data in order to determine the importance, scope, and attribution of research's effects. Evidence is defined as the communication or "demonstration" of impact based on rigorous analysis. However, identifying the benefits of research is a very subjective process, and a benefit for one group in a specific location, time, and culture may be interpreted as harming the interests of others (e.g. other groups, future generations or the environment). (Ferré, M., et.al., 2021).

Thus, evaluation or assessments were done to determine the impact of implemented programs, projects or activities. Such assessments would portray the outcomes, the strength and weaknesses which is the basis in deciding whether or not to continue. Same as in the law enforcement, there were a lot of initiatives implemented which are also subjected to assessment for the betterment of their services in achieving their mandates especially in the maintenance of peace and order and crime prevention.

Crime prevention is usually not the concern of everyone. Crime prevention is a series of strategies done by the national government to the local government units to combat crimes. These strategies may include mobile or foot patrol, imposing curfew hours, information dissemination,

and others. Additionally, the primary aim of crime prevention is to ensure the safety of the community. (Vicente, J. et.al., 2020).

The study Effectiveness of Fear and Crime Prevention Strategy for Sustainability of Safe City in Malaysia the strategy of crime prevention through social development (CPSD) recognizes the underlying complicated social, economic, and cultural processes that encourage crime and create an atmosphere of fear of crime. It attempts to bridge the gap between criminal justice programs and social support for communities, families, and individuals by preventing the causes that allow crime and victimization to happen. In other words, CPSD refers to social programs designed to solve the fundamental causes of crime: poverty, homelessness, inadequate parenting, issues with individual personality and behaviour, poor education, harmful peer associations, unemployment, substance abuse, cultural conflict, family dysfunction, social alienation, and unequal distribution of resources. In short, most of the CPSD programs are long-term, large scale strategies and criticized by as not suitable for short term policies and implementations. (Seng, B., et.al., 2020).

Kuzmin (2021) cited particular attention is paid to new theoretical directions in this area, such as identifying the places most susceptible to crime, calculating the algorithm for the actions of criminals and determining the places, routes, the time when criminals gather or carry out their criminal activities. Detailed knowledge of this information gives an idea of where and at what moment police officers can intervene to repress the crime, or take the necessary advance actions to prevent the crime. This method is based on focusing on the place and time of the crime. Crime is never completely random, criminal events and criminal behaviours are shaped according to a specific time and place. Thus, the essence of the theory of situational crime prevention is to eliminate provocations, reduce the possibilities of committing crimes and conditions facilitating crimes. Its main purpose is situational crime prevention or security measures.

In the Philippines, The National Police Commission is mandated by Republic Act 6975, or the "Department of Interior and Local Government (DILG) Act of 1990," to suggest a national crime prevention program to the President through the Secretary of the DILG. The NAPOLCOM's Technical Committee on Crime Prevention and Criminal

Justice, an ad hoc interdisciplinary organization comprised of recognized specialists from government and non-government institutions involved in the criminal justice system, established the 2019 National Crime Prevention Program (NCP). To ensure the NCP's success, the President's Office issued Memorandum Circular Order No. 66, directing all government departments and local government entities to support it.

In a study *Community Crime Prevention: The Case of a Barangay in the Northern Philippines*, Vicente et.al. (2020) Despite the low crime rate in the barangay, BCPO Station 3 personnel, barangay officials, and the community acknowledge challenges in the performance of crime prevention activities that need to be addressed to achieve better results. Also, the active participation of barangay volunteers should be encouraged through the leadership and management of the Purok Leaders. It would also help request from partner agencies and organizations of the barangay for assistance in the provision of equipment and crime prevention paraphernalia such as a baton, flashlight, whistle, reflectorized vest, raincoats, and boots together with the installation street lights at strategic areas. Lastly, during council meetings, the SK Council shall be reminded of their mandates.

Since 2016, the NEUST-College of Criminology Extension Services has carried out community outreach programs as part of its flagship program, PEACE is for Promoting Easy Access to a Crime-Free Environment, and it is a criminology project that strives to provide the community with an environment favourable to peaceful living through integrated programs. As a peace-making machine, the college of criminology believes that peace may be reached by educating and refining the community's knowledge of peace and order, particularly among our front-line personnel such as Barangay Tanods and Security Guards. As a result, the college executes numerous projects to promote peace with the university's unwavering support.

• **Objective:**

The primary aim of this assessment is to identify the outcome as well as to determine the economic, social, and environmental impact of the different extension services conducted and implemented by the College of Criminology over the last five (5) years (2016-2020).

II. METHODOLOGY

This is a descriptive quantitative study to determine the impact of the extension services conducted by the NEUST-College of Criminology for the past five years from 2016-2020. The study conducted in the City of Cabanatuan with 25 respondents identified through purposive sampling composed of 8 selected Barangay Officials, 8 Bantay Bayan and 9 Residents. Consent was secured from the respondents before the collection of data. Survey questionnaire validated by experts were used to gather data. Data gathered were tabulated, analysed and interpreted using Likert Scale and weighted mean.

A. *The NEUST-College of Criminology Extension Services*

The NEUST-College of Criminology Extension Services has implemented community outreach activities since 2016-2020 under its flagship program PEACE (Promoting Easy Access to a Crime-Free Environment through integrated programs).

Promoting easy access to a crime-free environment (PEACE) is a criminology project which aims to provide the community with an environment that is conducive for living harmoniously through integrated programs. The college of criminology as a machinery of peace makers believed that peace can be achieved by educating and refining the communities knowledge on peace and order especially our front liners such as barangay tanods and security guards. Hence, the college through the unending support of the university implements various projects to promote peace.

Under this program the following extension projects were undertaken; Violence against Women and their Children (VAWC) Awareness of Selected Barangays of Cabanatuan City, PEACE-Competency Enhancement of Barangay Public Safety Officers of Cabanatuan City, and Technical Assistance on Security Services NCII Assessment.

*B. Overall Impact***PEACE PROJECT****(Promoting Easy Access to a Crime-Free Environment through Integrated Programs)**

Outcome Indicators	Average	Outcome Probability
(Training skills I have learned apply in my chosen profession and in my career.) Angmganatutunangkanasanayansa training ay akingnagagamitsaakingnapilingpropesyon at libangan.	4	Likely
(Training skills have helped increase my income) Angmganatutunangkanasanayansa training ay nakatulongnamadagdaganangakingkita	3.56	Likely
(The training skills learned helped improve my self-confidence.) Angmganatutunangkanasanayansa training ay nakatulongnamapabutiangakingkumpiyansasasarili.	3.89	Likely
(The skills I learned in training I share with other people.) Angmganatutunangkanasanayansa training ay akingnaibabahagisaibangtao.	3.67	Likely
(The training skills I learned helped me get a job.) Angmganatutunangkanasanayansa training ay nakatulongupangmagkaroonakongtrabaho.	3.56	Likely
(I can use and benefit from the modern technologies I have learned in training.) Angmganatutunangmakabagongteknolohiyasa training ay akingnagagamit at npapakinabangan.	3.78	Likely
(The skills learned in the training helped me to start my own income.) Angmganatutunangkanasanayansa training ay nakatulongupangmakapagsimulaakongsarilikongpagkakakitaan.	3.44	Possible
Overall Average	3.70	Likely

Table 1

It can be gleaned from the table that the PEACE PROJECT (Promoting Easy Access to a Crime-Free Environment through Integrated Programs), has likely impact to the participants. It can be seen from the table that the overall average (3.70) implies that the respondents were likely able to use the skills learned to their chosen profession and hobby. It also helped them increase their income by finding a job relative to the skills learned from the extension projects.

The process of decision-making as an on-going activity that changes dynamically with the acquisition of additional information.(Abe, E.N. &Chikoko, 2020).Ghuangpeng, (2011) argued that the sector is mostly concerned with dealing with individuals. Thus, having a patient attitude and like dealing with people were highlighted as crucial personality attributes for a career in business, and they tended to rate their self-efficacy based on this perception. Meddour, H.et.al, (2016) personal interest has a great impact on career decision as it plays an important role on the choice of the profession an individual wishes to adopt. Individuals will try hard and put all their effort into making their dream career a reality. It means that the respondents were able to put their newly gained skills to use in their chosen career or hobby. It also helped them to earn more money by supporting them in finding work that utilized the skills they had learned via the extension programs.

C. *Economic Impact***PEACE PROJECT****(Promoting Easy Access to a Crime-Free Environment through Integrated Programs)**

Outcome Indicators	Average	Outcome Probability
(I was helped to find a job because of the skills I learned from the Extension Project conducted.) Nakatulunganakongmakahanapngtrabodahilsakasanayangnatutunannadulotngisinagawang Extension Project.	3.22	Possible
(It helped to increase my income as a result of the work because of the Extension Project conducted.) Nakatulongpangmadagdaganangakingkitablangresultangnakuhangtrabohonadulotngisinagawang Extension Project.	3.22	Possible
(It helped to improve the state of my life or my home as a result of the earned income from work by the Extension Project conducted.) Nakatulongnamapabutiangestadongakingtahananbilangresultangnakuhangkitasatrabohonadulotngisinagawang Extension Project.	3.22	Possible
(It helps to meet daily needs (e.g. food, beverages, etc.) as a result of the earned income from work because of the Extension Project conducted.) Nakatulongnamapunanangmgapangangailangansa pang araw-araw (e.g. pagkain, inumin, atbp) bilangresultangnakuhangkitasatrabohonadulotngisinagawang Extension Project.	3.22	Possible
(It helped to buy home requirements as a result of the employment gains generated by the Extension Project.) Nakatulongpangmakabilingmgakinakailangansabahaybilangresultangnakuhangkitasatrabohonadulotngisinagawang Extension Project.	3.22	Possible
(It helped to obtain ownership as a result of the earned employment income generated by the Extension Project.) Nakatulongpangmakakuhangmgapagmamay-ariblangresultangnakuhangkitasatrabohonadulotngisinagawang Extension Project.	3.22	Possible
(My children were able to help with education as a result of the work-related income generated by the Extension Project.) Nakatulongnapag-aralinangakingmgaanakbilangresultangnakuhangkitasatrabohonadulotngisinagawang Extension Project.	3.11	Possible
(It helped promote my family's health as a result of the work income because of the Extension Project conducted.) Nakatulongnamaitaguyodangkalusuganngakingpamilyabilangresultangkitasatrabohonadulotngisinagawang Extension Project.	3.11	Possible
(It helped promote the lives of relatives and friends as a result of the work income because of the Extension Project conducted.) Nakatulongnamaitaguyodangbuhayngmgakamag-anak at kaibiganbilangresultangkitasatrabohonadulotngisinagawang Extension Project.	3.11	Possible
(It helped improve the quality of life as a result of the employment income because of the Extension Project.) Nakatulongnamapabutiangkalidadngpamumuhaybilangresultangkitasatrabohonadulotngisinagawang Extension Project.	3.11	Possible
Overall Average	3.18	Possible

Table 2

It can be gleaned from the table that the project has moderate impact on the economic aspect of the participants' lives. It helped them realized their strength and weaknesses as peace providers and help them improve their quality of service to the community.

According to D., Heo K., Seo Y. (2020) rapid mobilization of public services was made possible thanks to a collaborative approach that leveraged networks across public agencies, community organizations, and citizen volunteers. As a whole, the extension project assists the community and front-line workers in improving their weaknesses and recognizing their strengths in terms of public safety.

D. Social Impact

PEACE PROJECT

(Promoting Easy Access to a Crime-Free Environment through Integrated Programs)

Outcome Indicators	Average	Outcome Probability
(It helped to be productive and make the right decisions as a result of the skills learned by the Extension Project.) Nakatulongupangmagingproduktibo at gumawangtamangdesisyonbilangresultangmgakasanayangnatutunangisinagawang Extension Project.	3.44	Possible
(It helped to share with the community and others the skills learned from the Extension Project.) Nakatulongnaibahagisapamayanan at ibaangmgakasanayangnatutunansaisinagawang Extension Project.	3.33	Possible
(It brought me to be a volunteer to be a good community citizen.) Nagdulotsaakinnamagingisangboluntaryoupangmagingisangmabutingmamamayannagpamayanan.	3.44	Possible
(It helps boost my confidence as a result of the skills learned by the Extension Project.) Nakatulongupangmapalakasangakingkumpiyansasarilibilangresultangmgakasanayangnatutunangisinagawang Extension Project.	3.44	Possible
(It helps me socialize with other people and get out of our homes to enjoy life.) Nakatulongsaakinnamakihalubilosabangtao at lumabasmulasaaminggatahananupangmasiyahansabuhay.	3.44	Possible
(It helps me improve my health and nutrition as a result of receiving and learning information.) Nakatulongsaakinupangmapabutiangakingkalusugan at nutrisyonbilangresultangnatanggap at natutunannaimpormasyon.	3.44	Possible
(It helps to establish friendships with other potential beneficiaries.) Nakatulongnamaitaguyodangpakikipagkaibigankasamaangiba pangmgamaaringmakinanabang.	3.44	Possible
(It provided an opportunity to celebrate the great aspirations of our community.) Nakapagbigayngoportunidadnamaipagdiwangangmagagandangadhikainngamingpamayanan.	3.44	Possible
(It helps to promote democracy, unity, diversity, and justice in any aspect of life.) Nakatulongnamaitaguyodangdemokrasya, pagkakaisa, pagkakakaib-iba, at hustisyasaalinmangaspetongpamumuhay.	3.44	Possible
Overall Average	3.43	Possible

Table 3

It can be gleaned from the table that the project has moderate impact on the social status of the respondents as can be seen from the overall average. The result of the study implies that the participants acknowledge that the project help them improved their relation to the community as front liners.

According to Hussain&Afzal (2020) prosocialbehavior can be seen in the form of community service through a service learning project where people not only help others, but also appreciate others through the notion of pluralism. That is why, according to Goodwin (2019), government, volunteer, and community group collaboration can be considered a form of coproduction. The PEACE Project or the extension project initiative assisted them in improving their front-line relationships with the community by exchanging information and experience through training and seminars.

E. Environmental Impact

PEACE PROJECT

(Promoting Easy Access to a Crime-Free Environment through Integrated Programs)

Outcome Indicators	Average	Outcome Probability
(The Extension Project carried out had a detrimental effect on the quality, flow, and any part of the water in the community.) Angisinagawang Extension Project ay nagdulotngmasamangepektosakalidad, daloy, at anumangbahagingtubigsapamayanan.	1.44	Never
(The Extension Project carried out has caused adverse effects on the animals living in the water part.) Angisinagawang Extension Project ay nagdulotngmasamangepektosamgahayopnananinirahansabahagitubig.	1.44	Never
(The Extension Project carried out caused pollution to the water or any part thereof.) Angisinagawang Extension Project ay nagdulotngpolusyonsatubig o anumangbahaginito.	1.44	Never
(The Extension Project carried out consumed a lot of water.) Angisinagawang Extension Project ay kumonsumongmaramingtubig.	1.44	Never
(The Extension Project has had a detrimental effect on air quality and flow in the community.) Angisinagawang Extension Project ay nagdulotngmasamangepektosakalidad at daloynghanginsapamayanan.	1.44	Never
(The Extension Project has caused air quality pollution in the community.) Angisinagawang Extension Project ay nagdulotngpolusyonsakalidandnghanginsapamayanan.	1.44	Never
(The Extension Project carried out had a detrimental effect on flying animals.) Angisinagawang Extension Project ay nagdulotngmasamangepektosamgahayopnalumilipad.	1.44	Never
(The Extension Project has affected the environmental cleanliness of the community.) Angisinagawang Extension Project ay nakaapektosakalinisanngkapaligiranngpamayanan.	1.44	Never
(The Extension Project has increased the amount of waste in the community.) Angisinagawang Extension Project ay	1.44	Never

nakadagdagsadamingbasurasapamayanan.

(The Extension Project has caused a problem with the community's waste.) Angisinagawang Extension Project ay nagdulotnngproblemasabasurangpamayanan.	1.44	Never
(The Extension Project carried out has had a detrimental effect on the animals in the environment.) Angisinagawang Extension Project ay nagdulotnngmasamangepektosamgahayopnanasakapaligiran.	1.44	Never
(The Extension Project consumed a lot of electricity.) Angisinagawang Extension Project ay kumonsumongmalakisakuryente.	1.44	Never
(The Extension Project has caused a shortage of electricity in the community.) Angisinagawang Extension Project ay nagdulotnngkakulangannngkuryentesapamayanan.	1.44	Never
Overall Average	1.44	Never

Table 4

It can be gleaned from the table that the projects has no negative impact on the environment, the projects implemented was in accordance with the safety protocols laid by the competent authorities and it did not harm the environment.

III. CONCLUSION AND RECOMMENDATIONS

It is then concluded that the NEUST-College of Criminology Extension Services has marked its impact to the community evident in the high overall impact. Hence, it is recommended that the college extension services continue and be strengthened by delivering initiatives that will have a greater impact on the community's lives.

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